

HISTORY OF TUTORING AND OBJECTIVES OF TUTORING IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF UZBEKSTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635935>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Tutor, education, tutoring activity, student, university, higher education, education system, upbringing.

ABSTRACT

In this article discusses the history of the emergency of tutoring and its stages of development in Europe. At the same time, there is talk about the introduction of tutoring in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the current state of affairs and objectives of tutoring in educational system of Uzbekistan.. The scientific article provides feedback and suggestions based on the success of the world's education systems.

Introduction

Currently, tutoring is a new method for the Uzbek education system. Uzbekistan has adopted this approach from the global education system, and the question is, of course, whether this activity will have a significant impact in our education system. In order to find an answer to this question, we think it would be expedient to first look at the history of the activity and study its shortcomings and achievements. Through this we can compare how activities based on previous experiences affect our education system.

The origin of the word tutor

Historically, the word of tutor is derived to English from word of French "tuteur" (guardian) and to French is derived from word of Latin "tueri" (to prevent). The root of the term is "tueri", which is derived from the ancient Sanskrit language and means strong [1]. From this we can see that

the term tutor is associated with the words "guardian", "defender" and "protector".

The term tutor is a word that came to Uzbek from English and means teacher, educator and his function is to help students develop personally, participate in university, national and international competitions and olympiads, and spend their free time meaningfully. He directs students to the profession, engages them in various scientific circles, identifies shortcomings and finds solutions to them. However it is important to keep in mind that tutoring is a historically shaped pedagogical process that helps students develop individual curricula and complements the individual learning process at the university, including extended education and continuing education.[2.250].

The emergence of tutoring

Tutoring entered the educational process unofficially, its history dates back to the

emergence of ancient city-states. By the XI th century, tutoring will have an official appearance. In the ancient Paleolithic period, when parents mentored children, by the end of the Paleolithic period, human beings were united into communities and small urban states began to emerge. It was at this time that human attention began to be focused on education. An example is ancient Mesopotamia and Egypt.

Of course, when it comes to education, it is impossible not to mention ancient Greece. During this period, great emphasis was placed on education, and each city-state had a different approach to education. For example, in Sparta, a child separated from his parents at the age of 7 and educated in special camps[3]. Ancient philosophers (Socrates, Plato, Aristotle etc) further developed the education system in period of ancient. Tutoring did not have an official appearance in this period, its main task was to develop science skills in pupils. Activity is called by different terms in each country, for example, pedagogue in Greece and tutor in Italy[4,89].

The introduction of tutoring in European universities dates back to the XII-XIV centuries. Tutoring as an institutionalised form of mentoring appeared at first British universities – Oxford (XII cent.) and Cambridge (XIII cent.). Main objective of those universities was educating of clergy who were basically the only literate class in Europe, participating in culture reproduction [5]

In later centuries, tutoring began to play a key role in students development. The tutor communicated with the student not only as a teacher but also as a friend or as a citizen. Another difference of the tutor was that they communicated with the students

not in a formal way but in love and fathered them by helping them spiritually.

By the 16th century, the tutor had become a figure in the middle of the university system, serving as a parent to students. He helped students to adapt in the early stages of the university education system and explained to students how to create student curricula, supervised them and prepared them for exams. He became the closest advisor and assistant to the students.

By the twentieth century, the study of tutoring techniques had grown exponentially, and Oxford scholar Will Moore made a number of determinations that tutoring was a triumph of the British educational experience. He states that tutor is not a teacher in its classical meaning: it is not his job to transfer the knowledge, student has to look for the information on his own. In this case teacher-tutor is a constructive critic who can help sort out the information, verify it, study possible ways of work and choose one approach over others. Will Moore finishes his work by following words: “When all the resources are directed for making the education efficient... it is doubtless that there is no substitute to individual lessons with a tutor. Function of a tutor is not to teach, but to set a goal to logically and reasonably communicate their thoughts, to help the student by critically analysing and revising of his work. ...” [6].

Currently, tutoring at Oxford and Cambridge universities plays an important role in the development of talent and spirituality. At present role of a tutor is changing as relationship between a tutor and a student shift to partnering. English educators are sure that a student can evolve into an expert only under conditions

of so-called close academic community, offering feedback systems between a student, a professor and the whole academic teaching staff. Here a tutor is a linchpin providing integrity of academic education [7].

Under the present British university system a tutor performs functions of: a curator performing classes management (organisation of schedule, holding tutorials, exams, consultations, control of academic progress, academic consultations); a professor, giving practical classes (seminars), consultations on specific topic, organising individual work of students, structuring of knowledge in a specific field, supervising research term work, organising intern program; a psychologist helping solve personal problems; a facilitator promoting maximum self-expression of a student through psychological support during the studies; a distance teacher. Such composition of tutoring work assumes following means for its realisation: individual and group consultations, conversations, tutorials (weekly classes), disputes, e-mails, seminars [8].

The main means of educating and parenting and a basic tutor's responsibility is creation of an effective individual educational program, which is subject to constant amendments and changes. Changes are made based on a joint analysis of success and advancement of a student on his path of studying. Fundamental notion of this pedagogics is a uniqueness of a human personality, of his or her purpose (including a professional one). This brings us to an individual approach to education.

During many centuries tutoring not became an anachronism of modern British education, but on the contrary took a

leading position in it. Having compared historical and modern forms of tutoring systems in Britain, we can draw a conclusion that after a long path of development tutoring saved its basic features of mentorship and made British university education classical.

At present tutoring is actively adopted by educational systems of many countries, in particular of Uzbekistan. In some countries, there are specialized tutoring courses for bachelors and masters in pedagogical universities[9].

Tutoring activity in Uzbekistan

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847, () tutoring was launched in our country. There are several goals in the organization of tutoring activities;

- Effective organization of education and upbringing;
 - regulating the relationship between the educational institution and the students;
 - better self-awareness, study and decision-making in life, increase love for chosen profession by providing socio-spiritual and psychological support to students;
 - strengthening the role of the Public Council and the community in improving the efficiency of the educational process at the institute, improving student attendance;
 - analyze students' mastery of the lessons and ensure that they spend their free time meaningfully;... [10].
- Through this goals we can know that expectations from tutoring activities are high.

Conclusion

From ancient time in our country great attention has been paid to the upbringing

of children. Our main goal was to bring up children who love their country and respect their parents. Tutoring is a new method that has entered our country by studying the achievements of foreign education systems, the main purpose of

which is to bring up a perfect person. Taking into account the education system of the above countries, we consider it expedient to open tutoring courses in undergraduate education in higher educational institutions of our country.

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